

Measuring Tissue Dispersion Using Optical Coherence Tomography Speckle

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ABSTRACT

Dispersion mismatch between the two arms of an Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) interferometer causes degradation of the image resolution. However, dispersion in tissue is specific to the chemical constituents of the cells and can therefore carry diagnostically useful information. Unfortunately, dispersion measurement techniques, presented so far in the literature, require the presence of strong distinct reflections in the OCT image which are rarely present when imaging tissues *in vivo*. The novel method presented here relies on the image speckle to calculate the PSF degradation and is therefore applicable to any tissue and can be implemented *in vivo* and *in situ*. The resolution degradation is estimated using a Wiener-type deconvolution and was verified *ex vivo* resulting in Group Velocity Dispersion (GVD) values comparable to the standard techniques. This technique has also been applied to normal and malignant samples of human colon to evaluate its applicability for cancer diagnosis. Using the statistics of the GVD estimate, the tissue classification resulted in 93% sensitivity and 100% specificity (96% correct classification rate). The success of these preliminary results indicates the potential of the proposed method which should be further.

1. INTRODUCTION

The wavelength dependence of the index of refraction in many materials results in the phenomenon of dispersion which causes pulse-width broadening with detrimental effects in many applications ranging from communications to imaging. In Optical Coherence tomography (OCT), dispersion mismatch between the two arms of the interferometer causes point spread function (PSF) broadening and, therefore, a degradation of the resolution. In order to eliminate the dispersion effects, several techniques have been developed, ranging from inserting materials or a prism pair in one arm to fiber stretching or even computational compensation [1-6]. However, dispersion is specific to the material that is causing the effect and can therefore carry useful information regarding its composition and/or concentration [7]. In tissue, dispersion could be used, for example, to detect changes associated with early cancer and result in more accurate disease diagnosis. Three main methods are described in the literature by which the dispersion can be estimated from OCT images: (i) measuring the degradation of the PSF [8], (ii) measuring the shift (walk-off) between images taken at different center wavelengths [8], and (iii) calculating the second derivative of the phase of the spectrum [9,10]. However, these methods require that a strong reflector is present in the image which might not always be the case in tissue. In addition, the presence of Mie scattering and speckle can be detrimental in the attempt to measure dispersion. In this summary, we propose a new technique for estimating the dispersion in tissue which uses the image speckle to calculate the PSF degradation and is therefore applicable to any tissue and can be implemented *in vivo* and *in situ*. The proposed method was verified *ex vivo* and its applicability to cancer diagnosis was evaluated on a small set of gastrointestinal (GI) normal and cancer OCT images. The results were very encouraging supporting further *in vivo* evaluation.

2. METHODOLOGY

A. Resolution Degradation

Dispersion can be measured from the degradation of the image point spread function (PSF). The pulse width of the original Gaussian resolution envelope t_r , and the broadened envelope, t_d , can be measured from distinct reflection in the OCT images and used to estimate the group delay dispersion (GDD) or the group velocity dispersion (GVD) [9] by

$$|GDD| = \sqrt{t_d^2 t_r^2 - t_r^4} \quad |GVD| = \sqrt{\frac{t_d^2 t_r^2 - t_r^4}{L^2}}$$

The GVD can be estimated only if the sample thickness, L , is either known or can be measured. This approach was used *ex vivo* to verify the results of the novel speckle method.

B. Ex vivo GVD measurement based on the PSF degradation

A swept source OCT system was used to image samples of a polymeric gel and porcine muscle and adipose tissue sections placed over a reflector which served as a reference for measuring the actual sample thickness and the resolution. Eight images were taken from different regions of each type of sample. For each image, the Gaussian width without

dispersion was measured from the free-space portion of the mirror (i.e. the portion not covered by the sample, Fig. 1A, blue line to the right). The broadened Gaussian width was estimated from the width of the reflector behind the tissue (Fig. 1A, red line). Using the location of the mirror, the actual thickness of the sample was also calculated as the distance between the top surface (Fig. 1A, green line) and the extension of the mirror line (Fig. 1A, blue line to the left). Based on these measurements, the GVD was estimated as the median of 250 measurements from individual A-Scans of each image. The standard deviation of the GVD of all images of each type was used as an estimate of the accuracy.

Figure 1. (A) OCT image of porcine muscle placed over a reflector (top surface: green, bottom surface: red, reflector: blue). (B) Zoomed portion of the bottom surface (red) with the FWHM (yellow). (C) The FWHM of the reflector calculated at each A-Scan.

C. GVD measurement using the tissue speckle

Due to its coherent nature, speckle in the OCT images is also affected by dispersion. The change in the speckle size due to dispersion can, therefore, be used to estimate the image PSF broadening and, subsequently, to calculate the GDD or GVD. However, the speckle size is difficult to estimate given the randomness of the signal. The approach used in this study was to divide the OCT image in smaller neighborhoods (twice the width of the system resolution, Fig. 2 A and B), containing mainly speckle, and to estimate the width of the speckle-PSF. To obtain a practical speckle-PSF estimation technique, a Wiener-type minimization was used. This was performed by substituting the speckle from the deeper portions of the image and the undegraded speckle from the top portion of the image into a Wiener deconvolution algorithm [11]. The result was the speckle-PSF image (Fig. 2 C) from which the mean width for all A-Scans was measured (Fig. 2D). The process was repeated as a function of depth (Fig. 2 E). The image PSF was estimated from a linear fit of speckle-PSF width, measuring the speckle-PSF degradation, and adding the same degradation to the original image resolution (Fig. 2 F). This technique was applied to the same samples as the standard method of section B and the results were compared to experimentally confirm the validity of the methodology.

Figure 2. (A) Portion of the image (80x250 pixels) containing mainly speckle from just below the top surface of the sample of Figure 1. (B) Similar portion from just above the bottom surface. (C) The result of Wiener deconvolution showing the speckle-PSF. (D) The width of the speckle-PSF for the 250 A-Scans in (C). (E) The mean speckle-PSF width as a function of depth with a linear fit (red line) illustrating the increase as a function of the depth. (F) The degraded Gaussian width as a function of depth calculated from the linear fit in (E).

D. Application of the speckle dispersion method on GI images

To demonstrate the applicability of the novel speckle-based method to human tissues, the technique was applied to images from normal and cancerous colon obtained from patients who were scheduled for surgical excision. Eleven normal and 14 abnormal images were included in this preliminary study. Since the actual tissue thickness could not be measured, it was estimated from the distance measured by OCT in air divided by an average index of refraction of 1.4 (error < 5%). The GVD was estimated up to a depth of approximately 0.5 mm (as measured in air) for 250 A-Scans per image (Figure 3). Using the statistics of these GVD measurements (such as mean, standard deviation, etc.) the samples were classified as normal or abnormal using Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) and leave-one-out-cross-validation (LOOCV).

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Table 1 summarizes the results of the GVD measurements using the standard PSF degradation (Section B) and the speckle-PSF (Section C) techniques described above. The values agree within one standard deviation (10-15%) experimentally verifying the validity of the speckle-PSF technique. The GVD measurements from the normal and abnormal GI tissues exhibit statistically significant differences (Fig. 4 A & B). The mean and standard deviation of these values were statistically different with p values of 0.03 and 0.002 respectively. Using the standard deviation of the GVD values, with LDA and LOOCV, the samples were classified with 93% sensitivity and 100 % specificity (96% correct classification). One example of the classification scatter plot is shown in the Fig. 4 C).

Table 1. GVD measured with the PSF degradation and speckle-PSF methods and mean index of refraction measurements

	PSF Degradation			Speckle-PSF			n		
	Median (fs ² /mm)	Std (fs ² /mm)	Std (%)	Median (fs ² /mm)	Std (fs ² /mm)	Std (%)	Median	Std	Std
Collagen	135.72	5.77	4.25	135.62	12.70	9.36	1.37	0.00	0.25
Muscle	136.97	16.62	12.14	133.08	13.59	10.21	1.43	0.03	2.19
Adipose	251.25	28.28	11.25	267.20	55.60	20.81	1.67	0.12	7.39

Figure 3. (A) OCT image of normal colon tissue (top surface: green, 0.5 mm depth: red). (B) Mean speckle-PSF width as a function of depth for (A). (C) Degraded Gaussian width as a function of depth calculated from (B). (D) Overlay of OCT image (gray scale) and GVD for each A-Scan (pseudocolor hue). (E-H) The same as before for colon adenocarcinoma.

Figure 4. (A) Distribution of GVD measured from normal and abnormal colon tissue. (B) The standard deviation of the GVD for each image. (C) LDA and LOOCV classification results of an unknown sample (cancer) which was correctly classified.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Given the results presented above, the GVD can be effectively estimated from the speckle-PSF degradation a technique applicable to any type of tissue *in vivo* and *in situ*. Such information could also be useful in the detection of tissue changes and could prove diagnostically useful. The success of these preliminary results indicates that further investigation is warranted, which should include both *ex vivo* and *in vivo* validation on a wider range of samples, to further elucidate the advantages and limitations of the proposed technique.

5. REFERENCES

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